

Pretreatment Effect of Physiological Dose of Melatonin on the Pattern of Nephrotoxicity by Ampicillin Sodium in Laboratory Animal Albino Rat, *R. norvegicus*.

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Introduction:

A number of experimental and clinical studies over past several decades have reported progressive structural and functional changes in the aging kidney (Meyer et al., 1989; Baylis et al., 1998; Epstein, 1996). There is probably more information today about age-related changes on kidneys than on any other organ system in the body (Meyer et al., 1989).

A number of environmental contaminants, drugs and renal ischemia dramatically alter these functions and produce multiple adverse effects (Cronin et al., 1986; Khundmiri et al., 1997; Goldman et al., 2006).

In this context, numerous authors published during last several years their findings about renal complications of drug therapy in the elderly subject. Marked structural alterations and decline in renal function also occurred during human aging in the absence of any specific renal disease (Rodríguez-Puyol et al., 1998 and Jassal et al., 1998). Spontaneous decline in glomerular function and structural injury is also observed in aging rats (López-Novoa et al., 1987). It is conceivable that, because of these changes, the aged kidneys are more susceptible to toxic substances than the kidneys from young individuals. With the idea that functional and morphological deterioration caused by xenobiotic substances or drugs can never be replenished completely during treatment in young age. Their profoundness increases abruptly at the old age causing vital organ failures. Thus it is wise enough to be precautionous and the ratio of oxidants/antioxidants during medication must be minutely observed. Increased free radical load must be under control by treatment of antioxidative agents which include different classes of compounds such as beta blockers, superoxide dismutase mimetic agents, hormones, iron chelators, vitamins and medicinal plants. The mechanisms of chemically induced nephrotoxicity have been studied mostly in young adult rats and so the information available concerning the susceptibility of aging rats to nephrotoxicant-induced damage is scarce and fragmentary, as Goldstein et al. already mentioned a decade ago (Goldstein et al., 1988).

In our previous chapter we have observed, that the treatment of ampicillin sodium (40 mg/kg body weight) to rats produced functional alterations in kidney and observed, renal toxicity could be due to high free radical load.

For many decades melatonin has been known as the major pineal secretory product but latter it has emerged as a compound that can also be synthesized in other organs and tissues and serves as an autacoid factor (Reiter et al., 2007). Endogenous melatonin is involved in many physiological functions; among them sleep promotion, circadian regulation, and modulation of immune responsiveness and control of reproductive activity in seasonally reproductive animals (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2006).

In addition, pharmacological amounts of melatonin effectively reduce oxidative stress through a number of mechanisms (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2006; Reiter et al., 2007; Tan et al., 2007). Melatonin has also been reported to increase the synthesis of glutathione and of several antioxidant enzymes. It is considered to be a broad spectrum antioxidant that is more powerful than glutathione in neutralizing free radicals and that can protect cell membranes from oxidative damage more effectively than vitamin E (Reiter et al., 1997).

The renal tissue is the main source of the excreted urinary enzymes and the evaluation of these enzymes level is known to be a good and sensitive noninvasive method to measure the tubular cells integrity (Jung and Burchardt 1987, Price RG 1982). These renal enzymes are characteristic and located at different specific sites as ALP is found on the brush border of proximal tubule epithelium.

Melatonin (N-Acetyl-5-methoxytryptamine) is a secretory product of the pineal gland as well as other select organs. It has been shown to be highly effective in reducing oxidative stress at many levels. Mechanisms involved in the protective effects of melatonin against oxidative stress involve direct free radical scavenging activity (Tan et al., 2002) and indirect antioxidant actions of melatonin (Rodriquez at al., 2004). Tan et al. (2002) have reported that under conditions of high oxidative stress *in vivo*, melatonin has proven superior to vitamin C and E in reducing oxidative damage.

The purpose of this experiment is to assess the protective effect of physiological dose of melatonin (25µ/kg body weight) by pre-treatment on the nephrotoxicity and free radical load caused by Ampicillin sodium

In this study, the nephrotoxic effects of ampicillin sodium on renal function, as evidenced by non invasive method imparted by changes in serum Creatinine and blood urea nitrogen (BUN) concentrations, acid & alkaline phosphatase renal brush bordered epithelial membrane cells of proximal convoluted tubule.

Kidney functional parameters such as ACP, ALP, urea and creatinine profile in blood and urine of rats and on free radical load by measuring total antioxidative status % (TAS%), lipid peroxidation products TBARs, SOD activity from kidney cortical tissue homogenates.

Materials and Method:

Twenty eight (28) adult male rats (weighing 150g to 180g each) were used for the present study obtained from the in-bred colonies of our animal house and acclimatized for one week in a room fully exposed to ambient environmental conditions (Light 12.50 hr; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The rats were housed in common rat cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had an access to standard rodent feed and water *ad libitum*. Later, they were divided into four groups of 7 animals each.

Group I: Control

Seven adult male rats were kept in natural environmental condition (NDL) as mentioned above without any treatment.

Group II: Ampicillin treated

Seven adult male rats were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of intravenous injection (through subclavian vein) of Ampicillin sodium

(40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in triple distilled water was given every day between 10:30 am and 11:00 am as mentioned in material & method.

Group III: Melatonin (25g/kg body weight) treatment.

Seven adult male rats were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. Melatonin (25g/kg body weight) was injected subcutaneously every day between 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset).

Group IV: Melatonin pretreatment and Ampicillin treatment.

Seven male rats were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. Pretreatment of a single dose of melatonin (25µg/Kg body weight) was given subcutaneously 5:00 to 5:30 pm (i.e. half hour before sunset) and one day prior to the intravenous injections of ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body weight). Melatonin injection dilution was prepared fresh every day as mentioned in Material & Method.

Sample collection:

The treatment was given for total seven days (i.e. total seven melatonin injection and seven plus seven melatonin followed by ampicillin injection). On eighth day i.e. after 24 hours of last treatment rats were sacrificed by decapitation after complete ether anesthesia. The urinary bladder was surgically extruded and emptied in a sterile tube by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min.

The experiment and handling of animals were performed in accordance with institutional practice and within the framework of revised Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act of 2003 and 2007 of Govt. of India on animal welfare.

Biochemical parameters:

Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the detection of superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level by (TBARS) method and total antioxidant status (TAS %). Trunk Blood was collected in separate heparinized centrifuge tubes for biochemical estimations of BUN, ACP, ALP and Creatinine.

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations.

Results:

Acid phosphatase activity: (ACP)

Ampicillin treatment significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased ACP in both serum (Fig: 1A) and urine (Fig: 1B) Melatonin treatment alone decreased ACP level and ALP level both in serum and urine. But a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease was noted in groups with melatonin pretreated rats along with ampicillin.

Alkaline phosphatase activity: (ALP)

Ampicillin treatment significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased ALP in both serum (Fig: 1C) and urine (Fig: 1D) but melatonin pretreated rats along with ampicillin recovered the increased levels of ALP and ACP, while melatonin treatment alone had no effect on Phosphatases level.

Urea:

A significant ($p < 0.01$) increase was noted in BUN (Fig: 2A) and urine urea (Fig: 2B) when treated with ampicillin but a significant ($p < 0.01$) recovered was noted in melatonin pretreated rats prior to ampicillin, while melatonin treatment alone had no effect.

Creatinine:

Ampicillin treatment significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased serum and urine Creatinine (Fig: 2C & 2D) respectively but a significant ($p < 0.01$) recovery was noted in melatonin pretreated rats prior to ampicillin, while melatonin treatment alone decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) creatinine in serum and increased ($p < 0.01$) in urine.

Total kidney cortical tissue protein:

Total kidney cortical tissue protein (Fig: 3A) increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) due to ampicillin treatment while a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease below the control level was noted in melatonin pretreated rats before the treatment of ampicillin, while melatonin treatment alone had no effect.

Lipid peroxidation level (TBARS):

Ampicillin treatment significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased TBARS level (Fig: 3B) while a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease was noted in melatonin pretreated rats before ampicillin treatment and melatonin alone decreased significantly ($p < 0.01$) below the control level.

Total antioxidative status % (TAS %):

Ampicillin treatment significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased TAS % (Fig: 3C) while a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease was noted in melatonin pretreated rats and melatonin alone increased significantly ($p < 0.05$).

Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD):

There was no significant change in superoxide dismutase activity on ampicillin treatment, but a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase was noted in both the melatonin treated groups and melatonin pretreated groups before ampicillin treatment.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1:

Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on Acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in (C) blood, (D) urine of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

Fig. 2

Fig. 2

Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on (A) blood urea nitrogen (B) urine urea and creatinine in (C) blood (D) urine of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

Fig. 3

(A) Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on the total kidney cortical protein weight of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

(B) Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on the malon-dialdehyde level (TBARS) of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

(C) Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

(D) Effect of Ampicillin and melatonin pretreatment (physiological dose 25µg/Kg body wt) on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of rats. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01; Control (control) vs Ampicillin treated (ampi), Melatonin treated (mel) and Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel) groups.

Plate 1

Fig. 4

Histomicrograph of rat kidney cortical region showing glomerulus (G), capsular space (→), Brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henle and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

A- Control (control)

B- Ampicillin treated (ampi)

C- Melatonin treated (mel)

Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (ampi + mel)

MEASUREMENT OF CAPSULAR SPACE (CS) OF BOWMAN'S CAPSULE AND LUMINAL SPACE OF PCT (20 SECTIONS/GROUP)

Treatments	Capsular Space (CS) of Bowman's cup	Luminal space of PCT
Control	10.82 ± 0.14 μm	10.28 ± 0.68 μm
Ampicillin sodium (40mg/kg body wt. i.v. in morning hours 11-12 am)	03.62 ± 0.14** μm	04.28 ± 0.68** μm
Melatonin (25μg/100g body wt. SC in evening hours 5-8.30 pm)	08.28 ± 0.84 μm	06.62 ± 0.58 μm
Melatonin + Ampicillin sodium (25μg/100g body wt. SC in evening hours 5-8.30 pm one day prior to the Ampicillin treatment)	07.45 ± 0.14 μm	09.96 ± 0.68 μm

Capsular space (CS) = Bowman's capsule - Glomerular capillaries diameter. Significance of difference ** p<0.01, Control vs Experimental groups.

Table 1

Discussion:

Reactive oxygen species and other free radicals are considered important mediators of renal cell injury by toxic insult and renal ischemia (Walker et al., 1999; Taulan et al., 2004).

A significant increase in LPO and alterations in activities of SOD, catalase and GPx are indicative of UN induced oxidative balance perturbation (Schramm et al., 2002). It appears that while increased SOD activity causes dismutation of generated superoxide radicals whereas increased glutathione peroxidase scavenges H₂O₂ and lipid peroxides produced as a result of antibiotic exposure. In addition, melatonin reduces the free radical induced alteration of microsomal membrane (SER, RER, and Golgi complex) fluidity during induced lipid peroxidation (Garcia et al., 1997; Longoni et al., 1998). A remarkable body of evidence indicates that melatonin exerts antioxidant protection in different experimental systems both in vitro and in vivo (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2006; Reiter et al., 2007; Tan et al., 2007). At physiological oxygen level, 1–2% of the O₂ consumed by the organism is converted to reactive oxygen species (Emerit et al., 2004). Melatonin activity includes up-regulation of antioxidant enzymes (glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, γ -glutamylcysteine synthase, glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase, superoxide dismutase and catalase) and down-regulation of prooxidant enzymes (NO synthases, lipoxygenases) (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2006; Reiter et al., 2007; Tan et al., 2007)

Considering the increase in superoxide dismutase activity and total antioxidative status observed after melatonin administration, the present study doesn't allow discerning whether the antioxidant effect is linked to a direct scavenging effect or to an indirect effect mediated by the improvement in the endogenous antioxidant protection systems.

Enzymes, such as ACP and ALP, are located in the brush border of the proximal tubule epithelium. The increase of the concentration of these enzymes in the urine denotes lesion in the brush border membrane and structural alterations due to loss of the microvillus, which reduces the reabsorption of proteins filtered (Scherberich JE, 1990). Increase in acid phosphatase activity indicates an increased number and size of lysosomes in proximal tubule epithelial cells as reported by histo-pathological studies by UN exposure (Haley et al., 1982).

Our findings show similar increase in ACP and ALP in both serum and urine on ampicillin sodium treatment. Inflammation can be initiated by different stimuli such as deposition or formation of antibody-antigen immune complexes, sensitized T-cells, trauma, tissue necrosis, or infection. It is characterized by activation of acute phase response and release of reactants/ markers such as C-reactive protein (Tripepi et al., 2005). Renal inflammation (glomerulonephritis and tubulo-interstitial nephritis) can occur either as an isolated local acute inflammatory reaction, or as part of a systemic inflammatory disorder, which usually results in interstitial dilation, tubular atrophy, and glomerular sclerosis in acute cases if not treated or spontaneously repaired. The local and infiltrating cells at the site of inflammation include activation, transition and plasticity of residential cells, adhesion, trafficking and activation of local and infiltrating inflammatory cells (neutrophils, monocytes/macrophages and lymphocytes) with the release of a wide variety of inflammatory mediators, which include different sets of adhesion molecules, proteases and degrading enzymes, oxygen free radicals, complements, nitric oxide, chemokines, growth factors and different types of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines (Karkar, 2004., Wardle, 2006).

The transient exposure of renal tubular epithelial cells and vascular endothelial cells nephrotoxic agents results usually in reversible impairment of functional activity of these cells, but can also lead to apoptosis; as the magnitude of these insults are below those required to induce rapid metabolic collapse and necrosis. By contrast, continuous exposure to these insults results in severe injury represented usually by acute tubular necrosis (Schena, 1998). The ampicillin sodium effect might be mediated by different sets of enzymes and liberation of free

radical mediated tubular damage from infiltrating inflammatory cells, in addition to some pro-inflammatory cytokines released from local and/or infiltrating cells.

More recently, the nephrotoxic effects of certain drugs such as flucloxacillin, penicillin G, and disulfiram have been found to be mediated through specific T-cells that are activated locally (within the kidney) and orchestrate a local inflammation via secretion of various cytokines (Spanou et al., 2006). The cause(s) of this ongoing micro-inflammatory process is not well understood, but it is accepted that continuous exposure to an inflammatory stimulus (e.g. uremia, oxidative stress and endotoxin exposure) results in local and systemic cell activation. Eventually, this produces different sets of inflammatory mediators that include cytokines, chemokines, and growth factors, CRP, vasodilators and vasoconstrictors, reactive oxygen species, and many degrading enzymes, in addition to activation of the complement system and expression of different sets of adhesion molecules (Jacobs et al., 2004).

Ethical clearance: All the experiment on animals were conducted in accordance with institutional practices within the framework of the revised animal (Scientific Procedures) Act of 2002 of Government of India on Animal welfare.

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